

RESEARCH ARTICLE

New Linear System in Fundamental Physics - Realization of a New Linear System Explaining the Fundamental Laws of Light and Energy in Infinite Spaces

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ABSTRACT

In doing this work, I try to better understand and understand relativity by giving it another form that better describes the relation between the energy of a particle and the speed of light (C) and I find a new parameter of time that I use it to explain deeper my theorem which is based on this newly exploiting aspect through a development of a special mathematical concept that gave me specific access to develop and bring out the energy theorem. I would also say that the theorem is a new mathematical and physical structure that is both linking and appropriate the C remains the same my concept just explained the phenomena that we can find them in far galaxies or even in our galaxy, as, for example, the black hole because at the level of these giant physical bodies matter it exists only in the state of emptiness with enormous speed and infinite time. Hence, I try to give a new concept for this coast.

Key words: Fundamental relationship, new fundamental physics, new relationship of energies, new time parameter, speed of light, universal infinite energy

INTRODUCTION

In this study, I put relations energy time and energy speed and material very developed to solve the classic theme of the equation of light and to come to make a new model of the equation of light by the hypothesis of creation of a new time parameter and a new concept which is based on this parameter which is a mathematical equation that I put them to get to make the new linear model of the equation of light in connection with the final time parameter.

DISCUSSION

Relationship sutured endless new.^[1-4]

The following new relationship that we have:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \infty = 1$$

Demonstrations were:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \infty = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum C * 1$$

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Or:

$$+\infty \prec C \prec 1$$

Hence, this implies the following relationship:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum C * 1 = 1^+$$

And:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \infty = \lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} \sum C * 1$$

Or we have:

$$-\infty \prec C \prec 1$$

This implies that:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} \sum C * 1 = 1^-$$

Or we have:

$$+\infty \prec C \prec 1$$

Moreover, it was for:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{+\infty}^{-\infty} \infty = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{+\infty} C * 1 + \lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} \sum_{-\infty} C * 1 + \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{+\infty} C * 1$$

Hence, the result is equal to:

$$1^+ + 1^- + 1^+ = 0 + 1^+ = 1^+ = 1$$

Hence, we have the end result is:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \infty = 1$$

Direct result of the physical fundamental law

In another demonstration, an equation which connects all the universal parameter of the universe between them this equation becomes:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \infty = 1$$

Moreover, it is known after the universal relationship:

$$\mu_0 \epsilon_0 C^2 = 1$$

And we:

$$E = mc^2$$

So we:

$$E/m = c^2$$

Was:

$$c^2 = 1/\mu_0 \epsilon_0$$

So we:

$$E/m = 1/\mu_0 \epsilon_0$$

Hence, we will:

$$\mu_0 \epsilon_0 E = m$$

Returning to our equation:

We have:

$$\lim \sum \infty = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 C^2$$

$$\lim \sum \infty = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 E/m$$

Moreover, we all at some point the universe tend toward a moment that I called:

$$T_F$$

So we:

$$\lim \sum \infty = T_F$$

So we:

$$\sum_{univers} \infty \rightarrow T_F$$

With:

$$T_F = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 E/m$$

We have:

$$c^2 = 1/\mu_0 \epsilon_0$$

And:

$$c^2 = E/m$$

So we:

$$T_F = E/mc^2$$

So we:

$$T_F c^2 = E/m$$

We set:

$$E/m \rightarrow E'$$

So we:

$$E' = T_F c^2$$

And we:

$$E = m c^2$$

So we will:

$$c^2 = E'/T_F$$

And:

$$c^2 = E/m$$

So we:

$$E'/T_F = E/m$$

Hence, we have the following general relationship:

$$E'm = T_F E$$

And with:

$$T_F = E/mc^2$$

So we:

$$E'm = E^2/mc^2$$

So:

$$E' = (E/mc)^2$$

And we:

$$E' = T_F C^2$$

So:

$$T_F C^2 = (E/mc)^2$$

So:

$$T_F C^4 = (E/m)^2$$

Hence, we have the following general fundamental relationship:

$$E = mc^2 \sqrt{T_F} \tag{x}$$

A relation can be deduced between E and E':

$$E = mc^2 \sqrt{E'/c^2}$$

So we:

$$E = mc \sqrt{E'} \tag{y}$$

Explanation of two theorems (x) and (y) dimension of a physical perspective;

For (x): I deduced the time and universe; is relative to the speed and mass of the materiel and energy E.

I was always positive because: $mc^2 \sqrt{T_F} > 0$

Hence, we can see that time very high compared to the speed and the materiel itself.

For (y): We have a new energy exist after time TF is universal infinite energy is always positive is proportional to energy E and it can reach the whole of the universe and explains the total flow of matter through transformation of these two energy.

Note: All these calculations are made to correct and retrieve a developed and corrective version of the classic Einstein relation and would be linked to a new time parameter that is T_F .

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